

‘Nō’ The Traditional Theater Of Japan

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Abstract

When it comes to Western theatre, the name that comes at the top is Greek theatre. Most things in the world have their origins in ancient Greece, whether it be literature, art, or philosophy. Greece had a rich civilization and a tradition. The origins of all these are considered to be from Greece, although many scholars have different perspectives. According to them, its origins lie in Eastern traditional theatre, where Indian theatre, Chinese theatre, and Japanese theatre are prominent. While Japan has a plethora of traditional theatrical forms, the tradition of these four art forms is still alive: 1. Nō Theater, 2. Kabuki Theater, 3. Bunraku Theater, 4. Butoh Theater

Keywords: Traditional, Nō Theater, Training Performing, Practice

Origin of Nō Theater:

The term "Nō" derives from the Japanese word "nō" which means "skill" or "talent." The origins of Nō are several thousand years ago, with claims of its development occurring in different stages such as the Nara period, Heian period, Kamakura period, Muromachi period, and eventually reaching the Edo period, where its form evolved. There are multiple interpretations regarding the origin of Sarugaku or Nō, with the first and most significant account found in the writings of Zeami Motokiyo.¹ According to Zeami's work, Nō emerged during the mid-14th century in the Muromachi period, and it was known by the name "Sarugaku"² at that time. Renowned actors, playwrights, musicians, and masters like Kan'ami

¹ Zeami Motokiyo was a Japanese Aesthetician, actor, and Playwrite. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Zeami_Motokiyo

² Sarugaku is known as Noh in the Modern period. <https://www.britannica.com/art/sarugaku>

Motokiyo (1333-1384) and his son Zeami Motokiyo (1363-1443) contributed to its development. Nō is a traditional theatrical form that originated from Japan's Shinto and Buddhist philosophies.

Nō incorporates two main elements in its performances, the art of dancing and the art of singing. Its subject matter primarily revolves around mythological stories and folk tales. The three main roles played in Nō are the Old Man, Woman, and Warrior. The main performer always keeps their face covered with a mask, which is typically made of wood.

The main stages of acting training in Nō Theater:

Traditionally, Nō artists provide training in Nō to their sons who are born into the family. Their fathers or grandfathers become their mentors and gurus, and they begin learning the various aspects of the art, discipline, and relationships associated with it from their adolescence. Nō training is essentially a lifelong commitment, as Zeami believes it to be a journey through bones, flesh, and skin. Bones are an excellent artistic quality that naturally manifests in the performances of talented actors because it is an innate ability. Flesh is an element that appears in the performance, generated by the power of the actor's skill. To acquire this power of skill, Nō actors must excel in two fundamental arts of chanting (Jap) and dancing (Nrittā) within Nō. Skin can be understood as a way of expressing ease and beauty in performance, which can be achieved when the other two elements are fully developed.

Kokata³ (Phase One)

This is the first phase of acting in which students, who are child actors between the ages of 6 to 12, learn chanting and dancing from the master teacher called 'Emoto.'⁴ According to Zeami When a boy practices at this age, some elements of beauty naturally appear in what he does.

³ <https://www.the-Noh.com/en/trivia/006.html>

⁴ Emoto is a leader or teacher in Japan. <https://tokyostages.wordpress.com/tag/junko-emoto/>

Uchideshi⁵ (Phase Two)

The most challenging phase of a student's life comes around the age of 23 and 24, and then the actor enters the most important phase of their professional life. Learning all the preparations and initial training backstage and acquiring mastery in it is as crucial as getting training for acting in this phase. Although there is no formal training for backstage work and preparations, student actors usually acquire expertise in it by observing and assisting senior members of the school during shows. Through this, students become familiar with costumes, packing and maintenance, necessary attire for an actor, transporting sets and props from one place to another, and maintaining appropriate communication with other artists. In summary, continuous and careful practice in this phase determines the future life of a student actor. The actor begins to excel not only in the arts of singing and dancing but also in the art of portraying roles. Training and physical development go hand in hand in this phase, and they become ready to play mature roles.

Jun-Shokobun⁶ (Phase Three)

According to Zeami when an actor reaches the age of 34 or 35, they represent the pinnacle of perfection in their art. If by that time an actor understands the various aspects of performance through rigorous training and attains mastery in them, they are truly acknowledged and gain prestige as a great actor. At this stage, they continue to practise everything they have learned so far. It is also a moment when they become capable of making plans to fulfil what they aspire to achieve in the future. An actor who reaches this phase is considered a professional veteran actor. Reaching this particular phase depends on the result of the dedicated training period that the actor undergoes in the previous phases. Instead of just showcasing their

⁵ <https://naginata-federation.eu/naginata-in-Noh/>

⁶ https://www.google.co.in/books/edition/The_Training_of_Noh_Actors_and_The_Dove/PdG3AwAAQBAJ?hl=en&gbpv=1&dq=Jun-Shokobun+in+Noh+theatre&pg=PA81&printsec=frontcover

skills in front of the audience, the actor has to focus on what they truly want to convey and accomplish.

The Second Part of Jun-Shokobun (Final Phase)

In this final phase, the actor's age ranges from 45 to 50 years. As Zeami suggests, at this stage, the actor needs to pay more attention to internalising their work and reducing external expression. By this phase, the actor attains comprehensive control over their body, which comes through continuous practice. As a result of body control, the actor reaches a state of naturalness that creates a sensitive state of grace. Reaching this state of mind and generating "Yugen"⁷ becomes the ultimate indication of true training for an actor in Nō.

Acting Style in Nō Theatre

The technique of acting in Nō theatre is based on movement and balance. The duration of a Nō play is typically about an hour. The text is poetic and spoken in the Japanese language. The singing portions in Nō are called "Utai," while the speaking portions are called "Kataru." Traditionally, most actors performing Nō were male, but nowadays both genders participate in it together.

An actor portrays a vast range of emotions and situations using only a small space, creating a sense of time and place. Within Nō's acting, there are three main roles played by actors. The first is the main actor called "Shite," the second is the supporting actor called "Waki," and the third is the comic actor called "Kyōgen."

Classification of Nō Plays

Nō plays are generally categorised into five groups. The first group is "Kami Mono" or God plays. The second is "Shura Mono" or Warrior plays. The third is "Kazura Mono" or

⁷ <https://www.britannica.com/art/yugen-Japanese-art>

Women's plays. The fourth is "Mono Kurui" or Madness plays. And the fifth is "Kiri Nō" or Demon plays.

Some Nō Plays Here are the names of a few Nō plays performed on the Nō stage: *ā* tsumori, Izutsu, Matsukaze, Kumagai, Takasago, etc.

The Stage of Nō Theatre

The stage of Nō theatre is made of wood and is referred to as the "Hon-butai"⁸ or Main Stage. It has a painted backdrop depicting various scenes. The stage area is approximately three-dimensional, measuring around three hundred and twenty square feet, with four pillars and a roof. Behind the stage (downstage) is the area where musicians sit. The floor of the stage is about three feet higher than the ground level.

Musical Instruments Used in Nō Theatre (Hayāshi)

The primary musical instrument used in Nō theatre is the flute, known as the "Nōkan." In addition to the flute, other instruments used include the "Kōtsuzumi" (a small shoulder drum), "Ōtsuzumi" (a large hip drum), and "Takio" (a drum).

Costumes in Nō Theatre

The costumes worn in Nō are called "Robes" or "Robes of Nō." According to "Konparu"⁹ (1983), they are exceptional in their design, colour, and appearance. The craftsmanship, embroidery, and patterns of these costumes are of great historical and cultural significance. The attire is an important element of Nō, adding to its attractiveness to the audience. The costumes worn by Nō actors, known as "Shozoku,"¹⁰ are generally divided into four categories. The "Kitsu-kerui" is an undergarment resembling a kimono. The "Uwagirui" is the outer garment, the "Hakamari" is a long trouser-like garment, and the "Obirui" is a sash-like

⁸ <https://www.the-Noh.com/en/world/stage.html>

⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Konparu_Zenchiku

¹⁰ <https://www.the-Noh.com/en/world/costume.html>

accessory. Additionally, the use of headgear known as "Kaburi-mono" is also common in Nō theatre.

Aesthetics of Nō theatre

The concept of "Hana"¹¹ (Flower) is considered the ultimate goal of a complete performance. Although the literary meaning of "Hana" is a flower, the idea of "Hana" was introduced by Zeami, who was developing the techniques of acting and training in Nō to depict the freshness and attraction of seasonal effects. This freshness and attraction are something that the audience has never seen before. As Zeami states, all plants and trees bloom in their appropriate season, and people admire their flowers because they are fresh and new. Similarly, in Nō, an actor should strive to impress the audience with freshness in each play and performance. All these flowers wither after a short time; it is not in their nature to remain for a long time. When they bloom in their appropriate season, they surprise people's eyes with their novelty and freshness. In Nō, "Hana" is the same freshness and novelty of an actor that attracts the audience.

Schools of Nō Theatre (Shite Kata)¹²

Five schools that are dedicated to preserving and teaching traditional Nō theatre-

1. Kanze School (Kyoto)
2. Kita School (Tokyo)
3. Konparu School (Nara region)
4. Hosho School (Ishikawa region)
5. Kongo School (Kyoto)

¹¹ <https://www.jstor.org/stable/41306514>

¹² <https://www.the-Noh.com/en/world/shite.html#:~:text=Nō%20is%20an%20art%20form,%3A%20shite%2C%20waki%20and%20ky%C5%8Dgen.>

Conclusion:

Nō Theatre continues to be performed today, preserving this ancient art form by UNESCO (United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization) as a Masterpiece of the oral and Intangible Heritage of Humanity. It allows the audience to experience the beauty and depth of traditional Japanese theatre. It creates the bridge between the past and present to know the real aesthetics of life. It is a journey through body , mind and space. Nō theatre is a rich art of actor's training, an art of constant practice that can be learned but never fully mastered. Mastery in itself is the final stage of anything, and theatre is the art of beginning life. Japan is one such country, because as small as this country is, its tradition is as big as it is.

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